

Communication in Social Marketing

Written by

Dr. Dalal Al-Dosari

27/2/2021

Communication in Social Marketing

Social marketing has gained importance in addressing a myriad of social and health issues. Communication in social marketing developed from a single dimensional reliance on announcements made through public service to become a rather sophisticated approach drawing from effective techniques and professional marketers, known as “social marketing” (Christensen, 2014). Social marketing developed in the 1970s as a discipline following a realisation by Philip Kotler and Gerald Zaltman that similar principles of marketing used in communicating products and the related brand values, could be applied in communicating attitudes, ideas, and behaviours.

The two define the concept of social marketing as being different from other aspects of marketing in as far as the marketer's objectives are concerned. In social marketing, the goal is to shape or influence social behaviour, not in a way that benefits the marketer, but for the benefits of the target audience or the public, in general.

Various social and public issues are targeted in marketing campaigns, among them being domestic violence. This paper is a marketing literature review which covers the key themes related to communication strategies related to domestic violence, covering issues related to the style, form and measurability of its impact.

Domestic Violence

In order to understand the important elements of communication to address domestic violence, it is important to understand what the problem is. Research has revealed the prevalence and negative effects of gender-based violence, in general, and domestic violence, specifically. Gender-based violence comes in various forms, and domestic violence is among them, others including sexual harassment and abuse, rape and trafficking among others. Nonetheless, there is one dimension that is normally forgotten by expert in social communication, the cultural and social norms that are mainly important in influencing people's behaviour, such as the tendency to use violence. The World Health Organization suggests that domestic violence, also referred to as intimate partner violence is the most common form of gender-based violence, taking the form of physical, sexual, emotional or psychological violence. This is a form of violence with deep social and cultural roots (Butchart et al. 2010)

Butchart et al. (2010: 11) defines it as “behaviour within an intimate relationship that causes physical, sexual or psychological harm, including act of physical aggression, sexual coercion, psychological abuse, and controlling behaviours”. In addition, this problem is a cycle which is normally very hard to break. However, through adequate information, it is possible to understand the scope and nature of the cycle of establishing the factors which causes it and come up with means of preventing it, and improving the health of individuals, families and communities. The harm that domestic violence causes is great and can last an entire lifetime, as well as impact on generations, , with destructive impact on health, employment, education, crime and economic health of persons, families and even communities.

Domestic violence is viewed as a significant constraint to development, retarding economic development and efforts to deal with poverty. Nonetheless, while acknowledging these facts, this form of violence is greatly invisible as it takes place in the private arena and normally seen as the element of female-male relationships. This form of violence occurs at home, and is perpetrated by relatives against their own, commonly by partners, parents and other relatives, and manifest in the form of physical, sexual and mental abuse. Commonly, women and are the victims of domestic violence, and commonly, the perpetrators are men. There is a major economic impact of domestic violence, as Butchart et al. (2010) suggests. This is in relation to average cost of goods and services that are used in the prevention of the problem, treatment and health needs of individuals affected by the violence process, and lack of productivity in the days lost from work by the victim. Apart from the general cost of domestic violence, the cost is even worse when it affects productivity, lowers human capital and weakens economic progress.

For the effectiveness in the use of the integrated communications strategy, it is necessary that the communication has a theme. Generally, the theme of a campaign to address the problem of domestic violence should directly relate to this objective (Butchart et al. 2010). The theme involves taking part in the prevention of domestic violence in the community. The message theme for such a campaign can be something like, Leading Change in Prevention of Domestic Violence.

The creative strategy depicts an understanding of the problem, its effects and interventions for the same. This creates the necessary awareness in the community and ensures that those receiving the message are involved in addressing the problem. Change of attitude and behaviour is the ultimate goal of the campaign and the same should be reflected in the theme. The theme is significant in a creative campaign and in creating the required positive relationship for the audience and achieves the necessary behaviour change. It should be attractive to the audience for the desired effect to be achieved (Christensen, 2014).

Behaviour Change Communication

Behaviour change communication is generally an evidence-based communication process that is consultative in nature, applied in addressing attitudes, knowledge and practice via identification, analysis, and segmentation of audiences, as well as participants in communication programs. This is achieved through the provision of important information, together with motivation, via well-defined communication strategies. The effectiveness of behaviour change

communication is informed by the use of an audience-appropriate blend of communication strategies and channels.

According to Insetta, et al. (2015) effective communication programs and the strategies they apply in achieving public health and social goals and objectives derive from both social science and epidemiological research. For example, social data provides insight on the 'why' of the issue. This means on why the people behave in the manner that they do. This data is usually informed and influenced by behavioural theories such as the diffusion of innovations. The data offers the lens through which to understand how the suggested behaviours are taken up by various persons within the target population over a time period. Behavioural analysis provides explanations on how behavioural and attitudinal challenges can be overcome to achieve behaviour change (Christensen, 2014). On the other hand, epidemiological data offers information on prevalence, distribution and problem control in the target population. It provides information on where the problem lies.

Insetta, et al. (2015) suggests that together with social and epidemiological information, evidence-based as well as scientifically organised and supervised strategic communication programs and interventions have to be connected to components of the program that related to service. For example, a communication program will strive to change attitude of the people on gender and such programs are not easily accessible. Therefore, for such kind of an initiative to work effective communication as well as service delivery part has to operate in unison in harmony. Communication has an artistic component that involves design of creative products and messages, and identifies successful interpersonal, group as well as media channels that are founded on adequate understanding of the target audience.

The behaviour change communication (BCC) is among the communication campaigns that can work with communicating the message on the negative effects of domestic violence. According to Christensen (2014) the main aim of behaviour change communication is to change the current knowledge, behaviours and attitudes of persons, families and communities, and at the same time facilitate and stimulate wider social change. The change can occur at the local, national or even international level. The change is reached through discussions with individuals and groups with the goal of informing, motivating and promoting behaviour change. Over the past two decades, various strategic communication programs have developed in mass and social media, resulting in more effective integrated community approaches.

Just in like in commercial marketing, the main emphasis in such a campaign to promote behaviour change is focused on the consumer; a group that is targeted with the message being communicated. Understanding of the audiences is a critical feature to improving the reach as well as effectiveness of such campaigns seeking to motivate social change. Theories and empirical research have developed pointing to the significance of people-centred, behaviour-oriented and strategic approaches to the campaigns. The message and information are very important aspects of strategic communication in addressing domestic violence. However, regardless the importance of the message and information being communicated, Christensen (2014) argues that it is important to look past the messages and seek to establish an environment in which inclusion of individuals can work.

Integrated Communication Strategy

The message designed to reach the target audience should be communicated. It is not enough that the campaign involves designing of creative and appealing message, while there is

no effective way of ensuring that the message is successfully conveyed. Various creative strategies are designed to communicate the message, just like in marketing of products and brands in commercial marketing. Designing a working strategy is necessary and entails a well-thought-out process involved in planning, developing, executing and evaluating coordinated, measurable, persuasive communication programs over time with the desired audience. Thus, various communication strategies can be effectively used in communicating the behaviour change message in the issue of domestic violence (Vine, Elliott & Keller-Olaman, 2010).

Effective communication strategies apply concepts ranging from the employment of advocacy and social mobilisation to psycho-social learning models related to role modelling conveyed through media to discussion with active participants. All these make up the important components in communication for the achievement of social and behavioural change. Most communication programs have for a long time emphasised on a metaphorical “tree” without adequate focus on the “forest”, that is, the attention was mostly on the person as the one requiring changing (Insetta, et al. 2015). However, for effective and large-scale change in behaviour, there are various aspects that should be targeted including negative societal norms cultural values, and structural inequalities; these aspects have to be considered. Effective communication strategies also have to put into consideration the policy as well as legislative environments and be related to various areas of service delivery in the society. For example, it is necessary that the strategies put into consideration services such as treatment and counselling for perpetrators and victims of domestic violence.

Vine, Elliott & Keller-Olaman (2010) suggest that different communication strategies have been implemented in the past, with varying effectiveness in addressing the problem of

domestic violence. Communication strategies including social mobilization, advocacy, interpersonal communication, participation development communication, public policy and media advocacy, mass communication, community empowerment, and entertainment education are among the approaches that have been developed for such purpose. However, Insetta, et al. (2015) suggests that there is no singular approach to strategic communication. Instead, what works better is use of a mix of suitable several communication approaches which are effective in fostering personal as well as social change, in what has come to be referred to as integrated communication strategy. Some of these strategies that have revealed a greater level of success and effectiveness in working together are discussed in the following section.

Social Outreach and Mobilisation

This is another communication strategy that has been and can still be effectively used in addressing the problem of gender violence. Also known as community mobilization, the strategy entails various approaches and interventions. According to Christensen (2014) such efforts like community meeting and training or sensitization sessions, form an important element of this strategy. Such efforts are necessary in discussing various issues related to domestic violence, including what domestic violence is, the common perpetrators and victim of the violence, the message to both the victims and the perpetrator, among other aspects of the problem. The primary objective of the strategy is to gain support from the communities and local authorities to support the efforts to achieve behaviour change. Social mobilization works a communication strategy for disseminating the important information in such a way that the audience is actively engaged to raise awareness amongst them. Some of the involved members of the community include service providers, social workers, teachers and community or religious leaders who

would in turn be involved in passing the information to the other members of their communities. The passing of information uses arenas such as street theatres as well as other cultural activities and demonstrations and marches.

Advocacy

Advocacy involves advocating for public policy and use of dialogue as a means of changing the cultural and social attitudes that lead to domestic violence and abuse in society. Such communications are developed with the goal of supporting the elimination of various forms of gender inequality and discrimination, including the use of effective legal and social frameworks. Advocacy is generally an integrated communication strategy that includes social mobilisation and media, with involvement of various stakeholders in form of individuals, institutions as well as community networks in strengthening their participation on various issues related to gender-based violence including domestic violence. Extensive social mobilization campaigns have worked in the past in dealing with various social and health issues such as HIV/AIDS. Advocacy is carried out in the efforts to achieve behaviour change and hope to reduce the problem in the involved communities (Christensen, 2014).

Interpersonal Communication

Together with social mobilisation and advocacy, use of interpersonal communication is an important approach to sending the message of domestic violence to achieve behaviour change and reduce the cases of the problem in society. The message is passed to the local people using those involved in the social mobilisation programs. This means that the healthcare providers,

teachers and local leaders are engaged in interpersonal communications with the other members of the community (Insetta, et al. 2015). The main goal is to increase the number of the people with the knowledge of the problem and in the end promote positive behaviours among the community members. This can be achieved by engaging in direct meetings with the members of the community to pass the message and information. Effectiveness is achieved in the event where the information contained has all the elements that should be known about the problem, including the effects and measures to address it. A holistic approach to issues associated with domestic violence has proven more effective in the past.

Media Campaigns

Media is the most common communication channel that is used to reach the target audience with the message. The most commonly used media is the radio, for the simple reason that it is the media owned and accessible to most members of society. With this media, it is possible to reach both the perpetrators and the victims of domestic violence. Also, the media can be used in sensitising the opinion leaders on the causes and effects of domestic violence. It is interesting to note that the media is the most commonly used strategy in training the media personalities to improve reporting on the issue (Insetta, et al. 2015). This is important considering the important role played by journalists in reporting various issues affecting society. Improvement from intensive training is important in enhancing this role in relation to domestic violence. Public awareness campaigns, as well as other interventions targeted to the public, are best conveyed using the media. Such, delivered through radio, television, and in the recent past, through social media reach and impact a great part of the community targeted with the message.

Media has always been effective in delivery of interventions meant for changing attitudes and behaviours. However, in using the media, it is important that the message and its delivery are carefully designed and developing. For example, family values can be communicated by using testimonies from couples, such as those that have successfully overcome the problem of domestic violence (Vine, Elliott & Keller-Olaman, 2010). Repetition is an important element that can be used in ensuring the positive impact of the message. Programs, such as soap operas can be used as they reach to emotions of the viewers through self-identification with the characters to alter negative attitudes and behaviours. The campaigns can be aired using billboards where the message can be posted for the public to view.

In the modern world, communication channels go way beyond the conventional channels such as radio and TV, as was the case in the conventional communication studies. This is due to the inclusion of other channels including the social media applications such as Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube among others. Thus, Christensen (2014) suggests the importance of communication professionals striving to reach the target audience using various channels in an integrated communication model. Mass media ensures that the message reaches a wider segment of the community, enhancing its effectiveness. The various channels provide individuals with access to important information as well as other resources without direct intervention of others including teachers or leaders.

Evaluating Impact

An integrated communication strategy that involves a blend of various individual communication channels has been found to be effective in the past in the achievement of behaviour change. Generally, Christensen (2014) argues that strategic communication is situated

in a unique place in fostering behaviour change goals and objectives and plays a critical role in overcoming the various handles revealed in the past to hinder behaviour change efforts. Strategic communication is revealed effective in facilitating both personal, as well as societal level changes. Effective behaviour change communication programs work by addressing the knowledge, attitudes and practices inherent in the target population. Use of channels including social mobilisation and advocacy work by contributing towards the development of an enabling political and social environment capable of supporting behaviour change, at the societal and individual level. Communication through the media is effective in the achievement of a lasting effect by communicating the relevant message to target audience.

Effectiveness of a communication program is evaluated through measurement of the achievement of the goals and objectives of the program. Such effectiveness of an integrated communications strategy is achieved through blending of the strengths of various communication strategies. They also work well by communicating to the community from different levels achieving greater impact. Use of a single channel cannot be effective in achieving the desired communication objectives (Vine, Elliott & Keller-Olaman, 2010). On the other hand, integrated strategies have worked in the past and will work in the future as long as the integration is seamless, such that the different communication and messaging tools are blended across different channels that are person-centred in nature. The main objective of this approach is to ensure that the various communication forms and messages are directly interrelated and work uniformly in the achievement of the overall objective of the campaign. The selected communication strategies will have to work together as a united whole toward achievement of the desired objectives. Such an approach also increases the credibility and

consistency of the message that is communicated. Consequently, an integrated strategy is better placed in appealing to the target audience and achieving the desired objectives.

Conclusion

Social marketing, just like communication in marketing involves sending a message to the target audience to achieve a desired objective. Such communication can be used for achieving an objective in dealing with social and health issues such as domestic abuse. The commonly used model in social marketing is behaviour change communication. The “behaviour change” discourse has been related greatly to social change in the modern research. However, while behaviour change models imply change at the individual level, use of integrated communication approach is more effective in achieving change at the individual and societal level, depending with the seamlessness of the integration. The approach works well by creating an environment capable for the social change to be achieved. Various communication strategies and channels are used to a consistent message to the intended audience. Effectiveness of such a program that uses an integrated approach is measured by its capability to achieve the desired objectives. This will be used in deciding whether the campaign is effective or not. Generally, various such communication campaigns have worked effectively in the past and will work if effectively implemented in the future.

References

Butchart, A. *et al.* (2010), in Waddell, T. (ed.), *Preventing intimate partner and sexual violence against women: taking action and generating evidence*, WHO and London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, Geneva

Christensen, M. (2014). Communication as a Strategic Tool in Change Processes. *Journal Of Business Communication*, 51(4), 359-385

Insetta, E. R., *et al.* (2015). Intimate Partner Violence Victims as Mothers: Their Messages and Strategies for Communicating With Children to Break the Cycle of Violence. *Journal Of Interpersonal Violence*, 30(4), 703-724

Vine, M. M., Elliott, S. & Keller-Olaman, S. (2010). To disrupt and displace: placing domestic violence on the public health agenda, *Critical Public Health*, 20(3): 339-355